

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: ESHIKENA****FIRST NAME: DOMINIC****PROGRAM CODE: DMCR****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references:

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 0%

The author used the following software: MSWord 2021 on Windows 10

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. Researching the topic (EUCLID 2021, 8-9)
2. Some rules of thumb for writing (EUCLID 2021, 12-14)
3. Punctuations (EUCLID 2021, 15-23)
4. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 33-39)
5. Style guide (EUCLID 2021, 40-42)
6. Sample correction to papers (EUCLID 2021, 66-71)

THE ART OF WRITING ACADEMIC PAPERS

1) INTRODUCTION

Writing is an art. Like many other arts, it involves careful planning. Anyone who understands cooking knows that a delicious meal does not result merely from a heap of ingredients. The timing of how ingredients are mixed and in what proportion the mixture occurs is crucial for producing palatable foods. The art of writing is similar to cooking.

Academic writing involves gathering resources and relevant information to address problems or provide evidence-based answers to research questions (EUCLID 2021, 7). The production of an academic paper, for instance, requires more than gathering resources. Having collected relevant materials, a writer must observe the specific style governing the various educational writing contexts.

The following paragraphs constitute my response to the study materials assigned for Period 1 of my first course at EUCLID, ACA-401D, in pursuance of a doctorate in Mediation and Conflict Resolution. The materials I will interact with are the course pack for ACA-401D, prepared by Prof. Laurent Cleenewerck and Dr. Kabiru Gulma, an

EUCLID Vimeo educational video presented by Prof. Laurent Cleenewerck on the Basic guidelines for writing and formatting a response paper, and a *YouTube* educational video by Dr. Kabiru Gulma on how to track changes in a Microsoft Word document of a response paper.

In this response paper, I will interact with the following aspects of writing an academic paper: researching the topic, some rules of thumb, punctuation, and plagiarism. Given the limits of a response paper, some relevant steps in writing an academic paper should be covered.

2) RESEARCHING THE TOPIC

The course pack is helpful regarding how to begin writing an academic paper. As a graduate student a few years ago, I faced enormous challenges when writing major essays. I realized what I was doing wrong as I read through the course pack for period one of ACA-401D (section on researching the topic). I have learned from this material to constantly focus my reading and research on seeking knowledge and evidence that will enable me to develop my thesis and then answer the question I am trying to address (EUCLID 2021, 8).

Researching the topic is a critical phase in writing an academic paper. However, this step can also be treacherous if one needs to be more disciplined in systematically sourcing and organizing the materials. One of the benefits of researching the topic while maintaining sight of the question one wishes to answer is that it facilitates the delineation of the paper into the tripartite division of introduction, body, and conclusion (EUCLID 2021, 10).

This section of the course pack is very helpful in researching a topic of interest in academic writing because it highlights the importance of being open to considering evidence that may not align with the writer's views. An open mind while researching a topic engenders creative and critical thinking without discrimination concerning the available evidence (EUCLID 2021, 9). A significant takeaway for me from this section of the course pack is that as I research a topic, I must never lose sight of the reason for the essay, which is "to provide answer(s) to hypotheses, aiming to communicate ideas based on evidence" (EUCLID 2021, 7).

3) SOME RULES OF THUMB FOR WRITING A PAPER

It is easy to lose focus when writing an academic essay. One of the things I have learned from the materials for period one of ACA 401D is the awareness and understanding of how to avoid some of the pitfalls in academic writing. The course pack provides rules of thumb that I will keep in mind when I write academic papers while studying at EUCLID.

One instructive rule of thumb that I found helpful in the course pack is the suggestion to avoid getting stuck with elaborate descriptions of theories intended to analyze particular problems (EUCLID 2021, 13). When there is an excessive elaboration of a

theory, a writer can avoid fatiguing the readers and ultimately losing them to wordiness and irrelevant information. Keeping the readers interested is one of the goals of academic writing. Context is essential; however, I must not allow the former to cause me to distract my readers and thereby mislead them (EUCLID 2021, 13)

Another insightful rule of thumb in academic writing that I found fascinating is clarity in writing. I realize that sometimes my sentences are long and complicated when writing. I learned from the course pack of period one of ACA-401D and Prof. Cleenewerck's *Vimeo* video that writers and readers benefit from clarity and brevity, which can be achieved using short and uncomplicated sentences (EUCLID 2021, 13).

Finally, the rule of thumb suggests taking the view one discusses seriously. This rule of thumb is significant for developing self-criticality for my ideas and empathy in my views of others in my writing. I also believe this rule can act as a guardrail for being aware of my assumptions when I write so that I can "develop a sense of internal integrity of my ideas and position" (EUCLID 2021, 14).

4) PUNCTUATIONS

Punctuations contribute immensely to the clarity of a writer's ideas, particularly in academic papers. No matter how much time one has invested in producing an essay, when punctuation rules are not observed, the essay becomes challenging to read, and even ideas may become convoluted. *The Chicago Manual of Style* instructively notes that "punctuation should be governed by its function, which in the ordinary text is to promote ease of reading by clarifying relationships within and between sentences" (The University of Chicago 2017, 364). However, getting punctuation right can be a nightmare for writers, and it has been for me. I often need clarification about my use of punctuation, especially commas. In period one of ACA 401D, I learned some basic principles that would help ease my difficulties with punctuation. For example, I often hesitate about *its*, and *it's*. The course pack has helped to resolve my confusion concerning when to apostrophize the word *its*; noting not to use an apostrophe when the context of the usage is possessive (EUCLID 2021, 16).

Another interesting highlight from the course pack concerns observing proper punctuation in bullet points. Reading the course pack helped me realize my errors in using punctuation in bullet points. I now know that "if texts inside the bullet point is a complete sentence in its own right, it is proper to add a semicolon to the end of each point" (EUCLID 2021, 18).

5) PLAGIARISM

A clear case of plagiarism can destroy everything a writer has done, regardless of the extent and depth of the work. "Plagiarism is one of the most important things the writer should do to avoid" (EUCLID 2021, 34). Any writer who disregards the strict rule concerning plagiarism does so at their peril. So, what exactly is plagiarism? According to

EUCLID (2021), "Plagiarism is when the writer uses a source of information without credit to the author of that source of information" (EUCLID 2021, 34).

Plagiarism amounts to academic dishonesty and a disregard for the intellectual property of other writers (EUCLID 2021, 34). I learned from the materials for period 1 of ACA-401D to avoid plagiarism. I need to, without exception, give citations and references to ideas that belong to others, whether I quote them directly or use the technique of paraphrasing (EUCLID 2021, 35).

The course pack for ACA-401D has been very detailed in describing plagiarism and how to navigate the danger using viable citation and referencing methods. However, EUCLID (2021) cautions against not having too many direct quotations in academic papers as a sign of the writer's originality. Instead, a writer should paraphrase. However, paraphrasing is more than merely replacing a few words in the original sentence. I am reminded that to properly paraphrase without plagiarizing, I must make the text I am paraphrasing my own – use my own words to express or explain the ideas of an author and then provide the appropriate citation.

6) THE ROLE OF STYLE GUIDE IN WRITING A PAPER

Sometimes, we can know what a thing is and does from its name - that is the case regarding the role of a style guide in academic writing. A style guide is an umbrella term that encapsulates the particular technical approach writers adopt based on the purpose and goal of the writing. Institutions of higher learning, publishing houses, newspapers, and web-based publications have distinctive styles (EUCLID 2021, 41).

One of the benefits of a style guide is that it allows several writers to coauthor articles or books since they can all follow agreed-upon rules and features that give their work a mark of consistency (EUCLID 2021, 41). I have learned from the course pack for ACA-401D and Prof. Cleenewerck's *Vimeo* video that at EUCLID, the recommended style is the Chicago Rules, otherwise known as Turabian (EUCLID 2021, 41). This information is a valuable guide as I begin to write response papers, quizzes, and major papers at EUCLID and beyond.

Although I cannot claim to have fully grasped the intricacies of the style guide, the course pack has put me on the right track in the direction of learning more about style guides in general, particularly the Chicago Rules. I hope to gradually gain more understanding and proficiency in using the Chicago Rules.

7) SAMPLE CORRECTION TO PAPERS

I must confess that I was confused and petrified before attempting to write my response paper for period one of ACA-401D. The impetus to start writing came from what I wish to refer to as practical guides (hands-on approach). The first was the section of the course pack on *sample corrections to papers* (EUCLID 2021, 66-71). The second resource

was the *Vimeo* video of Prof. Laurent Cleenewerck on "*Basic ACA-401 Tutorial*," which describes the basics of writing a response paper (Cleenewerck 2021). The final resource I found helpful in writing my first response paper was Dr. Kabiru Gulma's *YouTube* video, which addresses how to track changes in reviewing a response paper (Gulma 2022).

Writing this response paper has been a challenging experience for me. However, creating my first response paper at EUCLID was only possible with video resources and Dr. Gulma's Sample Correction to Papers.

8) **CONCLUSION**

As I conclude my response paper for the first period of the course ACA-401D, I acknowledge that while the exercise was challenging, it has benefited me immensely in three ways. Firstly, I have come to a better appreciation of the discipline of academic writing. Secondly, I have realized how little I know about the Chicago style guide and the need to spend more time getting acquainted with it during my studies at EUCLID. Thirdly, the experience of writing my first response paper has helped me to be more confident as I anticipate the rigors of academic writing.

The art of writing an academic paper involves more steps than I have addressed in this response paper. However, I would say that researching a topic, observing some basic rules of thumb, proper punctuation, making sure that appropriate citations and references have been made to avoid plagiarism, and using the Chicago style guide will help me as I proceed with my studies at EUCLID.

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